

COLLECTIVE TRANSBORDER COMMEMORATIONS AND PILGRIMAGE - THE CASE OF BULGARIAN CATHOLICS

Valentin Voskresenski

Pilgrimage has been an object of research of scholarly disciplines such as history, anthropology, religious studies, geography, sociology, tourism studies, etc. A large part of the studies has been carried out from the viewpoint of anthropology of religion (Turner and Turner 1978; Eade and Sallnow 2000; Coleman and Eade 2004; Badonne and Roseman 2004). In the context of such methodological approach, pilgrimage is interpreted mainly as a religious practice, which is also linked with popular culture, tourism and politics. The following elements of pilgrimage are outlined in the anthropology of Christianity: holy sites and their miraculous features; the perceptions, meanings, and ideas that pilgrims have; the religious practices through which they reach transcendental knowledge; the bodily pain and suffering that consolidate pilgrims; the exchange of symbolic meanings – from human to divine, from bodily to spiritual (Eade and Sallnow 2000: 1-29).

Pilgrimage is a religious practice, which has developed with Christianity ever since its appearance as a religion. Although religious trips in the first centuries A.D. differed from those in the Middle Ages, as well from those nowadays, over the centuries pilgrimages were always understood as being a religious act by which believers sought to perfect their faith (Gaya 2002: 11).

On the occasion of the great anniversary anticipated in 2000, the Pontifical Council for the Pastoral Care of Migrants and Itinerant People at the Holy See published a document, in which it pointed out the enormous significance that pilgrimage has had for the Catholic Church over the centuries (PCPCMIP 1998). The XIII Ordinary General Assembly of the Synod of Bishops bearing the title “The New Evangelization for the Transmission of the Christian Faith”, was again outlined the important role of pilgrimage and pointed out that it can also provide the occasion to introduce a person to a real experience of faith and to respond to the great existential questions which touch upon conversion in

one's life (Synod of Bishops 2012: 68).

Religious travels have become an important part of Catholic clergy's life ever since the spread of Roman Catholicism in Bulgarian lands. The clergy travel to get an education, to take part in religious events, to be ordained as bishops and to participate in the discussions of various Church issues. Unlike many of these missionary travels of Church clergymen, collective (group) pilgrimages of Bulgarian Catholics date back to the first quarter of the 20th century. During the communist regime, religious trips outside the People's Republic of Bulgaria were strictly limited, but after 1989 they developed progressively and appeared as one of the ways to overcome the isolation of the Catholic Church in Bulgaria. Their number increased as a result of the global migration processes and particularly after 2007 when the country was accepted as a member of the European Union. The pilgrimage visits changed the religious identity of Bulgarian Catholics and became a precondition of multicultural dialogue.

The goal of the current article is to trace the specifics of collective pilgrimage visits among Bulgarian Catholics and to point out their main purposes, organization and participant profiles. It attempts to define the importance of religious visits for the Catholic Church in Bulgaria in the context of globalization and migration processes. The paper analyses both the holy sites abroad that attract most Catholic pilgrims from Bulgaria and the sites that attract pilgrims inside the country. To prepare the article, the author has used interviews with Catholic priests in 2018, materials from the State Archives in Plovdiv, internet sources and periodical editions of the Catholic Church in Bulgaria.¹

Pilgrimage visits of Bulgarian Catholics before the mid-20th century

One of the earliest testimonies for carrying out group pilgrimage visits can be found in two brochures from the archives of the St. Augustine College, also called the French College, in the city of Plovdiv. The brochures were published in 1910 and today are preserved at the State Archives in Plovdiv.² One of the brochures was published with the idea to inform the Catholic community about the organized trip to Constantinople, during which a visit to the Bulgarian Exarchate was planned. The other brochure is related to a trip to Jerusalem. There is no evidence whether these pilgrimages were made and whether there was

¹ The empirical materials used in the text were gathered within the project "Constructing National Cultural Heritage Abroad: Transborder Pilgrimage and Commemorative Practices," funded by the Bulgarian National Science Fund.

² State Archives – Plovdiv (SAP), fund 186 K., archival unit No. 29, folder 1.

Bulgarian participation in them. The first positive evidence of pilgrimages made by Bulgarian Catholics was published on the pages of the Catholic publication “*Poklonnik*” [Pilgrim] from 1924, where it is mentioned that in the month of August there were “even some from Bulgaria” among the pilgrims who went to Lourdes.³ They went to the sanctuary to pray to Holy Mother of God and to receive “miraculous curing of their bodily diseases.”⁴ The next documented trips were in the Jubilee year 1925 when two groups of Bulgarian Catholics traveled to Rome. Their trip was with the purpose of “*earning indulgences during the sacred year.*”⁵ The journal “*Poklonnik*” published announcements to inform the Catholic community about the forthcoming visit: “*We are reminding all those who would like to go to a pilgrimage to Rome during this anniversary year to negotiate with N. Blagogov, O. N. Selimov – Catholic Church, Plovdiv.*”⁶ These trips and the preparations for them are described in detail on the pages of the Catholic publications “*Poklonnik*”, “*Istina*” [Truth], and in the Calendar “*Sts Cyril and Methodius*” from 1926.

The first group of these pilgrims was under the guidance of Father Nikola Selimov and consisted of 120 people. The pilgrims departed by train from the city of Sofia on July 6. They were sent off by a multitude of friends and were blessed by His Grace V. Peev. The pilgrims arrived in Rome on July 11, where they found accommodation at the Catholic facility “*Santa Martha*” together with pilgrims from Egypt and Tunisia. These Bulgarian pilgrims attended the beatification of Father Peter Julian Eymard at St. Peter’s Basilica, after which, on July 16, they were granted a personal audience by Pope Pius XI. The leader of the pilgrimage group delivered to the Pope a special greeting from His Majesty Tsar Boris III. The Pope himself, in his address to the Bulgarians, noted that “*...it is not an everyday event nor even a monthly event or an yearly event to see Bulgarian pilgrims in Rome...*”⁷

³ *Poklonnik*, No. 80, 1924, p. 8.

⁴ *Ibid.*

⁵ *Poklonnik*, No. 85, 1925, p. 3.

⁶ *Ibid.*

⁷ See more on this pilgrimage in: “*Nashite polklonnitsi v Rim*” [Our Pilgrims in Rome] – *Istina*, No. 12, 13–29 July, 1925, p. 4.

Photo 1. Bulgarian pilgrims in Rome. The photo was published in the journal "Poklonnik," No. 85, 1925, p. 81.

The same year a second great pilgrimage trip was made to Rome. The Catholic newspaper "*Istina*" noted that it was made due to the success of the previous one and because of it "...since in the month of July the villagers were busy with arduous farm work and could not go to Rome, and for that reason the Clergy leadership deigned to hear the voices of these sons of theirs as well."⁸ The group was led by His Grace Father Angel Badov and by the Apostolic Delegate to Bulgaria, Archbishop Angelo Giuseppe Roncalli, who was later to become Pope John XXIII.

The pilgrims departed on September 29 from the train station of the city of Sofia in a special train car. Before they reached Rome they visited Venice, Padua and Florence. About their stay in Florence, one of the pilgrims remarked: "*We saw so many monuments, so many art galleries in the homeland of Dante, and our feet could not stand it any longer.*"⁹ In Rome they were accommodated at the Pius X Institute and after which they visited Archbasilica of St. John Lateran, the Basilica Santa Maria Maggiore, Saint Peter's Basilica, the Basilica of Saint Paul Outside the Walls and the Basilica of San Clemente. On October 14 the Bulgarian pilgrims were received for an audience by Pope Pius XI, and on the return trip to Bulgaria they visited the town of Assisi.¹⁰

There was only one more pilgrimage trip to Rome in the first half of the

⁸ *Istina*, No. 14, 5 August 1925.

⁹ *Istina*, No. 27, 4 November 1925, p. 2.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*

20th century. It was made in 1929 and there were around 30 Catholics, among them 9 priests, who took part in it. In Rome the pilgrims visited the main sacred sites and were accepted for a meeting by Pope Pius XI.¹¹ In January 1937, an announcement about a specially prepared program for a forthcoming pilgrimage visit to the tomb of Jesus in Jerusalem, which was supposed to happen between April 18 and May 15 that year, appeared in the “*Istina*” newspaper. However, a later issue of the newspaper announced that the pilgrimage visit did not take place, as the “necessary number” of participants had not been reached.¹²

As regards their characteristics, these first pilgrimage visits of Bulgarian Catholics were guided both by the aspiration to pay a visit to certain sacred buildings and sites, as well as by the willingness to consolidate with Catholics from different parts of the country. The attempts to overcome the isolation and dispersion and to create contacts with the rest of the world were also expressed by the regular presence of the rubric in the “*Istina*” newspaper before 1944, which was dedicated entirely to “Catholics abroad.”

Socialist(-era) pilgrimages

After September 9, 1944, the Catholic Church in Bulgaria was subjected to numerous repressions and legal restrictions which made religious pilgrimages difficult. The warming of relations between the People’s Republic of Bulgaria and the Vatican in the 1960s was a determining factor for making some pilgrimages, which however were essentially communist party-related events, rather than religious ones. Thus for example on May 24, 1968, a group of 64 people, 22 of whom were representatives of the Orthodox and Catholic Churches in Bulgaria took part in a pilgrimage to the tomb of St. Cyril, and on May 25 the pilgrims visited the St. Peter Cathedral, the tomb of Pope John XXIII, after which they were granted an audience by Pope Paul VI. Historian Svetlozar Eldarov calls this trip “the first socialist(-era) pilgrimage” (Eldarov 2002: 113-116). In the following years Bulgarian Catholic priests took part in delegations to commemorations of the saintly brothers Cyril and Methodius, but these trips followed strict party and political guidelines and had a limited religious character. The pinnacle of this type of socialist(-era) pilgrimages was in 1975 when the First Secretary of the Central Committee of the Bulgarian Communist Party and Chairman of the State Council of the People’s Republic of Bulgaria, Todor Zhivkov, was received for an audience by Pope Paul VI. In

¹¹ *Poklonnik*, No. 140, 1929, p. 86. More about this pilgrimage visit see in: *Istina*, No. 27, 4 November 1925.

¹² *Istina*, No. 652, 21 April 1937.

the same year, Catholics from the three eparchies made the only pilgrimage trip during the socialist (communist) era. Priests, nuns, seminarists were granted permission to travel to Rome on the occasion of the Holy Year. On November 24 they paid their respect to the tomb of John XXIII in St. Peter's Basilica and to the tomb of Constantine-Cyril the Philosopher in the San Clemente Basilica. On November 26 they were received for an audience by Pope Paul VI. Before returning to Bulgaria, the pilgrims visited Assisi and Naples. These several examples comprise almost all the pilgrimage visits of Bulgarian Catholics during the socialist period.

Pilgrimage visits after 1989: from exception to everyday religious practice

After the fall of the communist regime in 1989 there was a genuine religious revival of the Catholic Church in Bulgaria. It came as a result of the passage of democratic legislation, restoration of congregations, restitution of expropriated property, building new churches, publishing of religious literature and introduction of new religious practices. Collective (group) pilgrimages is one of these practices. To date over 60 collective pilgrimages have been made with the participation of thousands of Catholics from Bulgaria. The pilgrimages increased after Bulgaria became a member of the EU in 2007. Since then, every year an average 4-5 pilgrimages have been made, and in 2015 their number was 7.

The growing number of pilgrimage visits after 1989 marked the end of the isolation of the Catholic Church in Bulgaria. The flourishing of this type of religious practices ensures conditions for spiritual development and fully-fledged church life of the Catholic communities in the country, as well as the reestablishment of the century-long tradition of communication with the Holy Father, the Pope.¹³ Religious visits turned into an instrument for restoring the congregations and the contacts with their missions, as well as enabling the dialogue between Bulgarians from different parts of the country and abroad.

Pilgrimages: purpose, organization, participants

Pilgrimage visits can be grouped on the basis of their purpose, ways of carrying out, length, participant profiles, personal motives for participation, etc. The increase of pilgrimage visits among Bulgarian Catholics allows the following typology. Depending on their purpose, they can be divided into trips

¹³ See Gradev 1994.

for visiting holy sites, audiences with the Pope, veneration of relics, travels on occasions of holidays, jubilee celebrations, beatifications and canonizations of saints, as well as such that are aimed at memorial sites linked with Bulgarian national cultural heritage abroad.

The vast majority of trips have complex character – they are not reduced to a single objective, but rather have a comprehensive nature, often combining different motives and pursuits. The object of pilgrimages to holy sites are usually churches, sanctuaries, tombs, monasteries and sites related to the lives of saints or to the history of individual Catholic orders. The holy sites gain special pertinence during anniversaries and jubilee celebrations, as well as during visits of the Pope. Such, for example, was the great anniversary in 2000 when thousands of pilgrims visited Rome. Such trips were made in 2004 to Dudeștii Vechi (*Star Beshenov*) on the occasion of the 200th anniversary of the Church of the Assumption of the Blessed Virgin Mary. In 2011, on the occasion of the Year of Apostle Paul, a pilgrimage was made under the motto “Tracing the steps of St. Paul” to Antakya, Turkey. In 2013, a pilgrimage trip was made to Edirne (*Adrianople*) on the occasion of the 100th anniversary of the Kingdom of Bulgaria in the Second Balkan War. In 2017, on the occasion of the 100-year anniversary of the Apparition of Mary in Fátima, a pilgrimage was made to Portugal in which some 230 laymen from different eparchies took part.¹⁴

Another major part of the pilgrimage visits is aimed at participation in an audience with the Holy Father. Such pilgrimages are made predominantly to Rome. Thus, for example, in 2001 a group of students, members of the Pelican Academic Spiritual Community at the St. Joseph parish in Sofia, undertook a pilgrimage trip to Austria and then to Italy, where on April 25 in Rome they were received by Pope John Paul II during his general audience and they received his blessing.¹⁵ Bulgarian Catholics were present at audiences with the Pope in 2009, 2013, 2016, etc. The audiences with the Pope have also been held during his various visits to countries near Bulgaria – for example to Greece and Ukraine in 1999, to Istanbul in 2015, as well as during the World Youth Days.

Another part of the visits has the purpose of paying respect to relics. Such were, for example, the pilgrimages of two groups of Bulgarian Catholics in 2010 who visited Turin to pay their respects to the Shroud of Turin. A similar trip was also that in 2018, made by a group of pilgrims from the town of Belene who traveled to Bergamo to pay their respects to the relics of Pope John XXIII.

¹⁴ The entire pilgrimage visit was recorded as a documentary: [youtube.com/watch?v=C2S-Ct7CMWM](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=C2S-Ct7CMWM) [Accessed 17 Mar. 2019], and [youtube.com/watch?v=u-l87jLy04M](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=u-l87jLy04M) [Accessed 17 Mar. 2019].

¹⁵ *Istina*, No. 6 (1330), June 2001.

Pilgrimage visits are also carried out on occasions of participation in beatification and canonization of saints. Bulgarian Catholics made pilgrimages to Rome on the occasion of the beatification of Bishop Eugene Bossilkov in 1998. Pilgrimages were also made in connection with the beatification of Pope John XXIII in 2000 and of Pope John Paul II in 2011, as well as on the occasion of their canonization in 2014. In 2015 and 2016 two pilgrimage visits were made under the title “In the steps of Pope John Paul II”, during which Bulgarian Catholics visited places linked with the life and work of the Pope in Poland. Such sites were the church of Ludźmierz and Tyniec, Oswiecym, the church of John Paul II in Lagiewniki, the Jagiellonian University, Wadowice, etc.

Another purpose of these pilgrimage tours is the visit of Bulgarian memorial sites abroad that are part of the national cultural heritage outside the country. Although Bulgarian memorial sites are not the major objective of these pilgrimages of Bulgarian Catholics, many of them become mandatory sites to visit included in their religious routes.¹⁶ In addition to Rome, the last few years have also seen a rediscovery of other “Bulgarian connections”, such as for example the Zeytinlik Thessaloniki Seminary, the Bulgarian Catholic High School in Edirne, the tomb of Bishop Nikola Stanislavov in Timișoara (Romania), the cathedrals in the town of Vinga and the town of Star Bișnov (Romania), the bronze portal of the Canton Valais in the town of Saint-Maurice (Switzerland), the tomb of Queen Giovanna of Italy in Assisi (Italy), the monastery La Salette (France) and others. In 2013, for example, on the occasion of the 100th anniversary after the defeat of the Kingdom of Bulgaria in the Second Balkan War of 1913, two groups of pilgrims undertook a trip to the Republic of Turkey, where they visited the building of the *Ss Cyril and Methodius* Bulgarian Catholic High School in Edirne, the “desecrated” grave of Bishop Rafail Popov, and the village of Akbunar (*Sarayakpınar*), which had a Bulgarian population until the Second Balkan War.¹⁷

In the last few years, there has been an increase in the number of travellers. In some of the groups their number reaches 350. In terms of confessional identity, the pilgrimage groups consist of Catholics, but there are groups that include Orthodox Christians and non-Christians. Some of the groups are predominantly made up of young people and sick people, but most groups are formed on parish, eparchy and national principle. The faithfulness of the

¹⁶ See more about these “Bulgarian connections” in Rome in the article of L. Gergova and Y. Gergova in this volume.

¹⁷ *Istina*, No. 7 (1476, July 2013, p. 6. More about the sites related to the Bulgarian Uniates in Eastern Thrace (Edirne) see in: Eldarov 2016; Vatashki 2007. About other significant Bulgarian sites abroad that are linked with Catholicism, see Teofilov 2015.

respective parish is taken into consideration when making the choice of the site for a pilgrimage trip. Thus, for example, the parish of Our Lady of the Rosary in Veliko Tarnovo prefers to organize “Marian pilgrimages” to Loreto (Italy), Fatima (Portugal), etc.¹⁸ Similarly, the parish of the Holy Virgin of Fatima pays special respect to the church of St. Fatima and to all sanctuaries linked with the appearance of the Holy Virgin in Fatima.¹⁹

With regards to their organization, except for the pilgrimages that are guided by the parish priests and by the separate Catholic congregations, there are also trips that resulted from the self-initiative of individual Catholics. Such are, for example, the annually held after 1989 pilgrimage tours to the Holy Land, which by their purpose and character are more akin to so-called “religious tourism” rather than religious pilgrimage.²⁰

The number of participants in the pilgrimage groups has changed too. In the first years after 1989 the groups of pilgrims were smaller and sometimes support was received from different organizations for organizing the tours. Thus, for example, the trip to Lourdes (France) in 1992, in which 14 young Bulgarians took part, was supported by the organization Lux et Caritas, whereas for other trips to the same site assistance was received from the French section of Pax Christi and the Catholic Committee against Hunger and for Development (CCFD), which covered nearly all expenses. In the following years, pilgrimage trips are organized with personal funds, and some receive assistance from Catholic organizations, such as the foundations Comunitas, Renovabis, Caritas, Pax Christi, UNITALSI and others.

Main pilgrimage routes of Bulgarian Catholics

The increased number of the visits after 1989 permits an outline of several main pilgrimage routes of the Bulgarian Catholics. The major destinations of pilgrimages are Jerusalem (Israel), Lourdes, La Salette (France), Rome, Padua, Loretto, Assisi (Italy), Częstochowa (Poland), Fatima (Portugal), Santiago de Compostela, Torreciudad (Spain), Marija Bistrica (Croatia), Medjugorje (Bosnia and Herzegovina) and others.

Since 1989, Rome appears to be the most attractive pilgrimage centre for Bulgarian Catholics. The sites visited are the seven pilgrimage basilicas – Saint Peter’s Basilica, Basilica of Saint Paul Outside the Walls, Basilica of Saint Lawrence Outside the Walls, Archbasilica of St. John Lateran, Basilica Santa

¹⁸ Interview with Father Strahil Kavalenov, FnAIF 2984 – No. 5.

¹⁹ Interview with Father Ventsislav Nikolov, FnAIF 2984 – No. 4.

²⁰ See interview with Stefan Ivanov, FnAIF 2984 – No. 7.

Maria Maggiore, Basilica of Saint Sebastian Outside the Walls, Basilica of the Holy Cross in Jerusalem. In their travel writings Bulgarian pilgrims also note their numerous visits to the Church of the Gesù, Trevi Fountain, the Holy Stairs which Jesus climbed to Pilate's Pretory in Jerusalem, the tombs of Apostles Peter and Paul and many others.

Another reason for Bulgarian Catholics to visit Rome are the audiences with the Pope. Such visits were made in 1994, 2001, 2009, 2013. Pilgrims from Bulgaria also travel to Rome to take part in religious events. Such events are the Jubilee year 2000, the beatification of the "Bulgarian Pope" John XXIII in the same year, the beatification of Pope John Paul II in 2011, the canonization of John Paul II and John XXIII in 2014, the canonization of Mother Teresa in 2016. Pilgrims from Bulgaria also head to the Eternal City on the occasion of religious events which are significant for the Catholic Church in Bulgaria. Such were the ordination by Pope John Paul II of Hristo Proykov as Bishop of the Apostolic Exarchate in Bulgaria in 1994 and the beatification of Bishop Eugene Bossilkov in 1998.

For Bulgarian Catholics pilgrimage sites are also the "Bulgarian connections" in Rome. It is mandatory for each Bulgarian pilgrimage trip to visit the Basilica of San Clemente where the tomb of St. Cyril is located. There are Bulgarian connections also in the Basilica Sant'Andrea delle Fratte where the tomb of Petar Parchevich is located, the Basilica Santa Maria Maggiore where the books of the saintly brothers Cyril and Methodius were consecrated by Pope Adrian II in the year 868. Other sites that are visited include the Main Passionist House, which houses a museum exhibit with relics of Bishop Eugene Bossilkov, the Chapel Santi Vincenzo e Anastasio and the tomb of the "Bulgarian Pope" John XXIII.²¹

Another important pilgrimage center for the Bulgarian Catholics is the Sanctuary in Lourdes, which is known for the healing properties of its water that appeared after the apparitions of the Virgin Mary to Bernadette Soubirous in 1858. In the 20th century the site became one of the most visited pilgrimage sites in the world.²² After 1989 more than 15 collective (group) pilgrimage trips have been made from Bulgaria to Lourdes, of which the largest were in 2000, 2006, 2009, 2012, 2013, 2015. Most were organized by the Order of Assumptionist Priests in the town of Plovdiv and by the parish of the Assumption of the Blessed

²¹ See more in: Gergova and Gergova 2017.

²² Detailed information about the establishment of the church in Lourdes as a pilgrimage center and about the links of the Congregation of the Augustinians of the Assumption with Bulgaria, see: Eade 2013: 51-77.

Virgin Mary in Sofia.²³ The pilgrimage trips are usually made in the month of August on the occasion of the Assumption of the Blessed Virgin Mary.

The first pilgrimage trip of Bulgarian Catholics to Lourdes after the political changes was made in 1992. The group consisted of 14 young people, aided by the organization Lux et Caritas. In 2003, a pilgrimage trip to Lourdes was made which included pilgrims from Macedonia, and in 2006 a trip was made with two buses, one of which with Orthodox Christians. An interesting pilgrimage trip to this destination was the one in 2009 when a group of 60 pilgrims took part in the Jubilee of the Assumptionist Priests in the Underground Basilica of St. Pius X in Lourdes. A reproduction of an icon of Bulgarian martyrs was placed in the basilica, and during the actual commemoration the pilgrims sang two Bulgarian songs – “*Lodka*” [Boat] and “*Himn za trimata blazheni*” [Hymn to Bulgarian Martyrs].²⁴

Photo 2. A photograph of a group of Bulgarian pilgrims singing Bulgarian songs at the jubilee celebration of the Congregation of the Augustinians of the Assumption in the underground basilica St. Pius X in Lourdes, 2009 (FtAIF 1733 – 2). The photograph was kindly provided by Ivanka Ivanova Georgieva.

In 2008, 2012 and 2015 on the initiative of father Blagovest Vangelov of the parish of the Assumption of the Blessed Virgin Mary in Sofia the first pilgrimage

²³ See more about the religious travels to Lourdes in: Eade 2012.

²⁴ See Zhilie 2009.

trips of this kind were made by sick people to the Sanctuary of Lourdes.²⁵ In the first one, the group consisted of 35 pilgrims among whom 5 in wheelchairs, and the remaining with varying degrees of disability. The second pilgrimage trip included Catholics, Orthodox Christians and non-Christians, among whom 12 registered as sick people and 8 in wheelchairs.²⁶ Both pilgrimage trips were made thanks to the Italian organization UNITALSI which facilitates trips by the so called “white train” furnished with railcars for people on life support systems and medication.²⁷

Photo 3. A group of pilgrims from Bulgaria in front of the Basilica of Our Lady of the Rosary of Lourdes, 2012. The photo was published in the blog “Usardie”: usardie.wordpress.com [Accessed 20 Mar. 2019].

The experiences during the pilgrimage trips to Lourdes become indelible memories for the participants: *“The experiences, the feelings and emotions, which I had during the liturgies, the prayers, the deeply meaningful songs, accompanied by wonderful sounds of the organ, the silence, the life-giving power of the water, the looks and touching of hands of acquaintances and strangers*

²⁵ About these trips, see the blog “Usardie” [Diligence].

²⁶ *Istina – Veritas*, No. 8 (1465), August 2012, p. 4.

²⁷ Further information about these trips, see in *Istina – Veritas*, No. 9 (1418), September 2008, p. 6, and in a film about the trip to Lourdes: vimeo.com/69321132 [Accessed 17 Mar. 2019].

from the thousands of good people in Lourdes – this is the greatest blessing, which I received forever!”²⁸ The impressions of Ivanka Ivanova Georgieva from Plovdiv, who described in tears what she experienced during her pilgrimage to the church of Our Lady in Lourdes are similar.²⁹

Another important destination of Bulgarian Catholics is the Jasna Góra Monastery in the town of Częstochowa (Poland) where the Black Madonna miraculous icon is kept. The first pilgrimage to this site was made on May 17, 1981, as a spontaneous protest against the assassination attempt against Pope John Paul II. The first pilgrimage trips of Bulgarian Catholics to the site were made in 2001. They were usually organized on the occasion of the Assumption of the Blessed Mary holiday. This pilgrimage trip differed from the previous trips in that it was made by foot and was a physical challenge in which not everybody was able to participate. The pilgrims covered the distance from Wrocław to Częstochowa in 6 days. This pilgrimage trip, like the one to the Sanctuary in Lourdes, provided intensive memories and experiences for the participants. Speaking about a trip in 2002 a Bulgarian pilgrim says: “...everyone’s heart was overflowing with love and contemplation, a feeling that until that moment we had only imagined, and then – having felt it – we found it difficult to describe it in words.”³⁰ A pilgrim remembering a trip in 2013: “Now words are inadequate to express what I experienced.”³¹

Under the influence of pilgrimage trips to Częstochowa, since 2011 parallel pilgrimage trips have been made in Bulgaria. Their route is from Sozopol to Malko Tarnovo, where the copy of the Black Madonna icon from the Jasna Góra Monastery is kept.³²

Except to reach certain holy sites, pilgrims also travel on occasions of annually held religious events. World Youth Days become popular pilgrimage events for Bulgarian Catholics after 1989.³³ During these gatherings young

²⁸ Ivanka Kirova, *Istina – Veritas*, No. 8 (1477), August 2013, p. 8.

²⁹ Interview with Ivanka Ivanova Georgieva, FnAIF 2984 – No. 2. Similar experiences are also presented in the documentary “In the steps of faith” (author: Marina Stancheva), which features the pilgrimage to Lourdes in 2015 – [youtube.com/watch?v=BHP9FMRMddg](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BHP9FMRMddg) [Accessed 20 Mar. 2019].

³⁰ *Istina – Veritas*, No. 9 (1345), September 2002, p. 8.

³¹ *Istina – Veritas*, No. 8 (1477), August 2013, p. 4.

³² Further information about the Marian cult, the sacred site in Malko Tarnovo, and the pilgrimage visits associated therewith, see in: Mihaylova 2003; Zovchak 2014; Mihaylova 2014; Niedźwiedz 2005; Niedźwiedz 2010.

³³ The world meetings of youth were held for the first time in 1985 as a continuation of the youth meetings to celebrate the Community Day that existed in Poland since the 1960s. The world meetings of families took place for the first time in 1994 and since then such meetings have been organized once every three years.

people from around the world meet the Pope. They are held every 2 years at different locations in the world. Young Bulgarian Catholics have participated in World Youth Days in Częstochowa (1991), Paris (1997), Rome (2000), Cologne (2005), Madrid (2011), Kraków (2016). In the past few years the number of participants in these meetings has been increasing significantly and some 350 young people from Bulgaria took part in the XV World Youth Day in 2016 in Kraków (Poland).

Three groups of young people from the three eparchies departed from Bulgaria to attend the XV World Youth Day in Rome in the Jubilee year 2000. Each group consisted of some 50 young people who passed through various towns, sanctuaries and holy places to gather back together in Rome.³⁴ This way of travelling was also chosen during the XIII World Youth Day in Madrid in 2011, when 2 groups from Bulgaria departed and travelled along different routes.³⁵ World Youth Days are pilgrimages in their nature, since the participants in them not only travel, but are also forced to suffer privation and make sacrifices.

Along with the World Youth Days held abroad, annual National Youth Christian Days have been held in Bulgaria since 2013. These events were attended by hundreds of young Catholics from different parishes – Malchika (2013), Sofia (2015), Belozem (2018) and others.

Pilgrimage visits in Bulgaria

The trips that groups of Catholics started undertaking among the different parishes in the country became something natural after 1989. Religious trips of this type are made for church holidays, anniversaries, jubilee celebrations, ordination of priests, the promotion of some Catholic places of worship into sanctuaries, guest visits of high-ranking priests, and religious excursions.

Tours of this type are also made in connection with the rediscovery of important dates and events related to the history of the separate congregations – e.g. memorial sites related to the beginning of the Uniate movement in Bulgarian lands.³⁶ Such is the case with the pilgrimage to the Sokolsky monastery Assumption of the Blessed Virgin Mary (Gabrovo region) in 2010, on the occasion of the 150th anniversary after part of the Bulgarian population joined the Catholic Church. Laymen from different parishes joined the pilgrimage and travelled to the site to honor the founder of the monastery, Joseph Sokolsky,

³⁴ *Istina – Veritas*, No. 10 (1320), September 2000.

³⁵ *Istina – Veritas*, No. 10 (1455), October 2011, p. 5-6.

³⁶ See more about the genesis of the Uniate movement in Bulgarian lands in: Vatashki 2007, 2011; Eldarov 2016.

who was consecrated as archbishop in 1861 by Pope Pious IX.³⁷

Another example of religious travel in the country on the occasion of a significant event was that to the town of Russe in 1998, in relation to the beatification of Bishop Evgeniy Bossilkov. For the occasion, young people from the entire Nikopol eparchy gathered in Russe on 14 November – “*representatives of the villages of Bardarski Geran, Gostilya, Malchika, Belene, Oresh, Tsarev brod, and from the town of Pleven arrived with special buses. The excellent organization permitted these almost 150 people to feel as one whole and to direct their thoughts to the affiliation they have with Catholicism*” (Karadzova 1998: 8). Another occasion for pilgrimage trips was the visit of Pope John Paul II to Bulgaria in 2002, when pilgrims not only from the country, but also from Croatia, Romania, Macedonia, and Poland, arrived in Plovdiv to meet the Pope and to attend the beatification rite that he held for three Assumptionist priests – Kamen Vichev, Yosafat Shishkov, and Pavel Dzhidzhov (John Paul II 2003: 87).

The increased number of travels abroad inevitably stirred the aspirations to build pilgrimage centers in Bulgaria. This process is facilitated not only by the recreation of holy sites, but also by the promotion of some Catholic places of worship into sanctuaries. As a result, they receive various blessings – relics, miraculous icons, consecrated statues, etc. – and become attractive centres for pilgrims from Bulgaria and abroad. The first sanctuary of this kind in Bulgaria is the Church of the Blessed Virgin of Lourdes in the town of Plovdiv, which was declared a sanctuary by a decree of Mons. Georgi Yovchev in 1995. The sanctuary houses a statute of the Virgin Mary consecrated by the Pope. The site is visited by pilgrims on the 11th of the month and mainly during the Church feast – February 11.

Photo 4. The Church of Our Lady of Lourdes in the neighborhood of “Kyuchuk Parizh” in Plovdiv. Photo: Valentin Voskresenski, 2018.

³⁷ See kae-bg.org/?act=news&do=detailed&id=31 [Accessed 20 Mar. 2019].

The second sanctuary is located in the town of Belene. It is the Church of the Nativity of the Blessed Virgin Mary which was declared a sanctuary of Bishop Eugene Bossilkov by a decree of Petko Hristov, Bishop of Nikopol, in 2000. The sanctuary houses a baptismal font of the martyr and a reliquary containing a piece of his shirt covered with his blood while he was awaiting the execution of his death sentence in Sofia City Prison in 1952. Next to the church there is a building constructed to house the Eugene Bossilkov Museum and Cultural and Educational Centre, intended to preserve the memory of the totalitarian regimes. Bulgarian and foreign groups visit the sanctuary throughout the year and its patron's holiday is November 13. The site is visited annually by foreign pilgrims who are attracted to it as a result of the activity of the Eugene Bossilkov Cultural Center, whose Statutes envision "*the creation of conditions for developing the pilgrimage tourism in the region.*"³⁸

The third sanctuary is the Church of the Holy Trinity in the town of Malko Tarnovo. It houses relics of the blessed Tselina Bozhentska – founder of the Congregation of the Resurrection Sisters in Bulgaria and a copy of the icon of the Virgin Mary from Częstochowa. The icon is the one consecrated in 2002 by Pope John Paul II. The church was declared a sanctuary of Pope John Paul II in 2014, after a capsule containing the blood of the saint was placed in it. In 1934 the site was also visited by the Apostolic Delegate Angelo Roncalli who later became Pope John XXIII. Under the influence of the pilgrimage from Wrocław to Częstochowa, since 2011 an annual pilgrimage trip is made between Malko Tarnovo and Sozopol.³⁹ The distance covered by foot is around 90 kilometres and there are participants from Bulgaria and Poland.

The fourth sanctuary in Bulgaria is the Church of the Blessed Virgin Mary of Fátima in the town of Pleven, which was declared sanctuary of the Virgin Mary of Fátima in 2016. On the occasion of the 100th anniversary of the apparition of the Virgin Mary of Fátima relics of the coffins of Jacinta and Francisco – two of the children before whom the Virgin Mary appeared in Fátima in 1917 – were brought to the church. The church houses a figure of the Virgin Mary of Fátima blessed by Pope Francis in March 2016. On the occasion of the feast day of the sanctuary, May 13, a large procession is organized in front of the church with the statue of the Virgin Mary and rosary praying.

The increased number of pilgrimage visits of Bulgarian Catholics after 1989 and the formation of pilgrimage culture have been the reason for the creation of many similar structures resembling the visited sacred sites. As a result of the

³⁸ See the Statutes in: bosilkov.com/bg/pages/tsel-63 [Accessed: 19 Jan. 2019].

³⁹ *Istina – Veritas*, No. 10 (1455), October 2011.

pilgrimage trips to Lourdes, there are many replicas of the Lourdes Cave made in Bulgaria. There are such in the churchyard of the Monastery of the Eucharist Sisters in Sofia, in the churchyard of the Monastery of the Benedictine Sisters in the village of Tsarev brod (Shumen region), in the churchyard of the Church of the Blessed Virgin Mary of the Rosary in the town of Veliko Tarnovo, in the centre of the village of Zhitnitsa and in many other places.

Photo 5. Replica of the cave of Our Lady of Lourdes in the village of Zhitnitsa. The cave and the plaque were unveiled in 2012 at the initiative of Prof. Stefan Ivanov and the Similarity of Our Lady of Lourdes Foundation. Photo: Valentin Voskresenski, 2017.

Conclusion

The presented materials allow the conclusion that the small number of pilgrimage visits of Bulgarian Catholics in the 20th century was due to several reasons, the major ones of which are related to economic factors, the wars in the first half of the century and the difficult post-war situations, as well as to the period of the totalitarian regime with its policies targeted against religion. The formation of pilgrim culture among Bulgarian Catholics started only after 1989. Unlike the religious trips that were held until the middle of the 20th century, which had the purpose of unification of Catholics in Bulgarian lands, in the years after the fall of the totalitarian regime, pilgrimage visits became an instrument to overcome the isolation of the Catholic communities in the country and to strengthen the links with Catholics around the world. Parallel

to the increased number of these visits, pilgrimage practices inside the country also started taking place.

The significance that pilgrimage visits have for the Catholic Church can be summarized in the following way: 1) Transborder religious pilgrimages are one of the instruments of restoration of the Catholic Church after the communist regime (1944-1989). Through them, the relations of the Catholic Church in Bulgaria and the Holy See have been restored, stronger relations have been built between the congregations in the individual countries as well as between the individual parishes and eparchies in the country. 2) Through pilgrimages, the existing holiday system of Catholic communities in the country has been modified. Making pilgrimages becomes a high point in the pastoral year, as a result of which the traditional is being replaced by the supranational and the multicultural. 3) Through annual pilgrimages new religious practices are introduced which aim to reconsider the pilgrimage experience and to integrate it within the Catholic community. Visiting sacred places and sanctuaries, coming into contact with relics of saints, participation in liturgies with many thousands of attendants strengthens the piety of Bulgarian Catholics, their faith and Christian culture. 4) As a result of the pilgrimages abroad, Bulgarian Catholics form their own pilgrimage culture, recreate holy sites, create sanctuaries and conditions emerge for pilgrimages within the country, which makes their faith even stronger.

Religious pilgrimage travels map a new sacred topography for Bulgarian Catholics, create a pilgrimage culture and shape local religious cults and traditions. In a personal aspect, they reaffirm the devotion to God of the faithful, provide an opportunity to rediscover new sacred places (churches, sanctuaries) and sacred objects (icons, relics, statues) and to create new spiritual connections to new saints and martyrs. In an environment of global mobility, religious pilgrimage travels play an increasingly important role in the everyday life and in the culture of the faithful and become a determining factor in creating multicultural dialogue.

ABBREVIATIONS:

FnAIF – Audio Fund at the Archive of the Institute of Folklore.

FtAIF – Photo Fund at the Archive of the Institute of Folklore.

PCPCMIP – Pontifical Council for the Pastoral Care of Migrants and Itinerant People.

REFERENCES:

- Badone, E. and Roseman, S. (2004). *Intersecting Journeys: the Anthropology of Pilgrimage and Tourism*. Chicago: University of Illinois.
- Coleman, S. and Eade, J. (2004). *Reframing Pilgrimage: Culture in Motion*. London: Routledge.
- Eade, J. (2000). Order and Power at Lourdes: Lay Helpers and the Organization of a Pilgrimage Shrine. In: Eade, J., M. Sallnow, eds., *Contesting the Sacred. The Anthropology of Christian Pilgrimage*. Urbana and Chicago: University of Illinois Press.
- Eade, J. (2012). Pilgrimage, the Assumptionists and Catholic Evangelisation in a Changing Europe: Lourdes and Plovdiv. *Cargo*, 10: 1-2, pp. 27-46.
- Eade, J. and Sallnow, M., eds. (2000). *Contesting the Sacred: The Anthropology of Christian Pilgrimage*. Urbana: University of Illinois Press.
- Eldarov, S. (2002). *Balgariya i Vatikana 1944-1989 [Bulgaria and Vatican 1944-1989]*. Sofia: Logis.
- Eldarov, S. (2016). Bylgarskoto uniatstvo v Odrinska Trakia (1860-1913) [Bulgarian Uniat in Eastern Thrace (1860-1913)]. *Trakia*, 7, pp. 14-42.
- Gaya, J. (2002). Pilgrimage in the Catholic Church Pastoral Care Structure. – *Peregrinus Cracoviensis*, 13, pp. 11-18.
- Gergova, L. and Gergova, Y. (2017). Cultural Heritage on Foreign Territory: Bulgarian Monuments in Rome and Bucharest. *Papers of BAS. Humanities and Social Sciences*, 4: 1, pp. 3-17.
- Gradev, V. (1994). Eho ot praznika v Rim [Echo from the Holiday in Rome]. *Istina [Truth]*, 2 (1237), p. 2.
- Karadzhova, S. (1998). Tryabva da prostim ot Boga silata da zhiveem zaedno vsichki [We Must Forgive from God the Power of Living Together]. – *Flamis*, 11/12, pp. 8-9.
- Mihaylova, K. (2003). "Malkoto otchestvo" na polyatsite v Bylgaria ["The Little Fatherland" of the Poles in Bulgaria]. *Nauchni trudove na Plovdivskiya universitet "Paisii Hilendarski" [Scientific Works of Plovdiv University "Paisii Hilendarski"]*, 41: 1 – Philology, pp. 131-138.
- Mihaylova, K. (2014). The Ritual Year of the Contemporary Polish Migrant Community in Bulgaria. In: D. Parusheva, L. Gergova, eds., *The Ritual Year 8. Migrations*. Sofia: Paradigma, pp. 274-285.
- Niedźwiedz, A. (2005). *Obraz i postać. Znaczenia wizerunku Matki Boskiej Częstochowskiej*. Kraków: Wydawnictwo Uniwersytetu Jagiellońskiego.
- Niedźwiedz, A. (2010). *The Image and the Figure: Our Lady of Częstochowa in Polish Culture and Popular Religion*. Kraków: Jagiellonian University Press.
- PCPCMP (1998). Pontifical Council for the Pastoral Care of Migrants and Itinerant People. The Pilgrimage in the Great Jubilee. Strathfield, N.S.W.: St. Pauls Publication vatican.va/roman_curia/pontifical_councils/migrants/documents/rc_pc_migrants_

doc_19980425_pilgrimage_en.htm [Accessed 21 Mar. 2019].

Teofilov, I. (2015). Bylgarskata sleđa [Bulgarian Trail]. *Istina [Truth]*, 3 (1496), p. 3.

Turner, V. and Turner, E. (1978). *Image and Pilgrimage in Christian Culture: Anthropological Perspectives*. Oxford: Blackwell Publishers.

Vatashki, R. (2007). *Bylgarskata pravoslavna tsyrkva i rimokatolicheskite misii v Bylgaria (1860 – 30-te godini na XX vek)*. *Tsyrovno-istorichesko izsledvane [The Bulgarian Orthodox Church and the Roman Catholic Missions in Bulgaria (1860-1930s). Church-Historical Research]*. Veliko Tarnovo: Faber.

Vatashki, R. (2011). *Bylgarskata pravoslavna tsyrkva i rimokatolicheskata propaganda v Bylgaria i Balkanite (IX – 30-te godini na XX vek)*. *Tsyrovno-istorichesko izsledvane [The Bulgarian Orthodox Church and the Roman Catholic propaganda in Bulgaria and the Balkans (IX-1930s). Church-Historical Research]*. Veliko Tarnovo: Faber.

Zhilie, D. (2009). Edno poklonenie ne kato predishnite [A Pilgrimage Different from the Previous Ones]. *Istina – Veritas [Truth – Veritas]*, 10 (1431), pp. 2, 8.

Zovchak, M. (2014). Ot pridvorna devoyka do devstvena feministka. Antropologichni izmereniya na Bogorodichniya kult [From a Maid to a Virgin Feminist. Anthropological Dimensions of the Virgin Mary Cult]. *Balgarski folklor [Bulgarian Folklore]*, 3, pp. 238–261.